

Re-inventing universal gravity law from a second Kepler's principle of planetary motion

Agnius Vasiliauskas, 2021

Abstract. Kepler's second law - covering constant ellipse sector area within a unit time - is pretty much well known fact. However as it is stated, it is likely a geometrical principle, rather than a physical one. Also it is hard to understand root causes why covered area per unit time is constant. In this paper I try to map Kepler's second principle into a more physical one, which explains better the root causes of phenomena and gives more insight into gravity law.

Kepler's second law can be stated as :

$$\frac{dA}{dt} = \frac{r^2}{2} \frac{d\theta}{dt} = \frac{r^2}{2} \omega = \mathbf{const} \quad (1)$$

where r is distance to planet and ω - planet angular speed. Angular speed can be expressed in terms of centripetal force :

$$\omega = \sqrt{\frac{F}{mr}} \quad (2)$$

Substituting equation no (2) into (1) and raising to the power of two, gives :

$$\frac{r^3 F}{4m} = \mathbf{const} \quad (3)$$

Inverting given fraction (3) and multiplying both equation sides by $(\frac{16}{3}\pi)^{-1}$ gives :

$$\frac{m}{4/3\pi r^3 F} = \frac{m}{V_e} \frac{1}{F} = \mathbf{const} \quad (4)$$

where V_e is planet's enclosing sphere volume with sun at the center. Noticing that first multiplier is nothing more but orbital mass enclosing density, gives final relationship :

$$\frac{\rho_e}{F} = \mathbf{const} \quad (5)$$

So when orbital mass density increases (due to decreasing enclosing sphere volume), so does increases gravitational force proportionally too. And under stronger gravity - planet is forced to have a greater centripetal acceleration, which causes an increased tangential speed of planet.

Enclosing sphere mass density can be best understood with a picture :

Thus planet covers same ellipse area in the unit time span due to the fact that orbital mass density is balanced by a gravity force. Also from equation (5) universal gravity law can be re-stated as a linear relationship:

$$F_G = \alpha \rho_e \quad (6)$$

where α is some proportionality coefficient having units of $\left[\frac{m^4}{s^2}\right]$.

Conclusions. From a second Kepler's law - constancy of covered ellipse area per unit time - another constant relationship (5) was derived which may explain Kepler's second law in a better and more physical way. Using relatively new concept - orbital mass density - redefinition of universal gravity law was achieved (6) as a linear relationship, which may help to shed more light on gravitation and may show a way into solving multiple-body gravitational problem.